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C-H Activation and CuAAC Reactions with 1,8-Naphthyridine Based Dicopper Complexes from a Computational Perspective

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A - C-H activation of alkyne by 1^+

The following figures are scatter plots showing the potential correlations between descriptors and the energy barriers. All the transition states related to the TS_1 series are represented in blue dots while the ones related to the TS_2 series are in green dots.

Figure A.1. Energy of the TSs as function of the position of NTf_2^- . No point has been removed.

Figure A.2. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu_1 and Cu_2 , $R^2 = 0.7080$. Four points were off the trend and have been removed: [2.95;39.9], [3.58;27.3], [3.74;24.2] and [3.91;33.3].

Figure A.3. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between C_1 and C_2 , $R^2 = 0.0047$. Three points are not shown for clarity: [3.63;31.8], [3.72;35.8] and [3.81;35.2].

Figure A.4. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between C₁ and H, R² = 0.0016. No point has been removed.

Figure A.5. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between C₂ and H, R² = 0.0178. Three points are not shown for clarity: [1.98;31.8], [2.07;35.8] and [2.21;35.2].

Figure A.6. Energy of the TSs as function of the dihedral angle between Cu_1 , N_1 , N_2 and Cu_2 , $R^2 = 0.0556$. One points is not shown for clarity: [-21.33;34.5].

Figure A.7. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of Cu_1 , $R^2 = 0.2178$. No point has been removed.

Figure A.8. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of Cu₂, R² = 0.0009. No point has been removed.

Figure A.9. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of the natural charge of Cu₁ and Cu₂, R² = 0.0073. No point has been removed.

Figure A.10. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of C₁, R² = 0.3447. No point has been removed.

Figure A.11. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of C₂, R² = 0.0000. No point has been removed.

Figure A.13. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of the natural charge of C_1 and C_2 , $R^2 = 0.2176$. No point has been removed.

Figure A.14. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of H, $R^2 = 0.1261$. No point has been removed.

Figure A.15. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of the natural charge of C₁ and H, R² = 0.1370. No point has been removed.

Figure A.16. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of the natural charge of C₂ and H, R² = 0.0490. No point has been removed.

B - C-H activation of alkynes catalyzed by water

1) Step A: the formation of 4^+

The following figures are scatter plots showing the potential correlations between descriptors and the energy barriers. All the transition states related to the TS_3 series are represented in blue dots while the ones related to the TS_4 series are in green dots.

Figure B.1. Energy of the TSs as function of the position of NTf_2^- . No point has been removed.

Figure B.2. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu_1 and Cu_2 , $R^2 = 0.0754$. Two point are not shown for clarity: [4.00;19.6]. [3.67;20.60].

Figure B.4. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between C₁ and H, R² = 0.0260. No point has been removed.

Figure B.5. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between O₁ and H, R² = 0.0122. No point has been removed.

Figure B.6. Energy of the TSs as function of the dihedral angle between Cu_1 , N_1 , N_2 and Cu_2 , $R^2 = 0.0918$. No point has been removed.

Figure B.7. Energy of the transition states as function of the natural charge of Cu_1 , $R^2 = 0.0017$. No point has been removed.

Figure B.8. Energy of the transition states as function of the natural charge of Cu₂, R² = 0.1642. No point has been removed.

Figure B.9. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of natural charge between Cu₁ and Cu₂, R² = 0.0337. No point has been removed.

Figure B.10. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of C₁, R² = 0.0512. No point has been removed.

Figure B.11. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of O₁, R² = 0.0227. No point has been removed.

Figure B.12. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of natural charge between C₁ and O₁, $R^2 = 0.0549$. No point has been removed.

Figure B.13. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of H, $R^2 = 0.0281$. No point has been removed.

Figure B.14. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of natural charge between C_1 and H, $R^2 = 0.0012$. No point has been removed.

Figure B.15. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of natural charge between O_1 and H, $R^2 = 0.0924$. No point has been removed.

2) Step B: the formation of 2^+

The following figures are scatter plots showing the potential correlations between descriptors and the energy barriers. All the transition states related to the TS_5 series are represented in blue dots while the ones related to the TS_6 series are in green dots.

Figure C.1. Energy of the transition states as function of the position of NTf_2^- . No point has been removed.

Figure C.2. Energy of the transition states as function of the distance between Cu_1 and Cu_2 , $R^2 = 0.7559$. No point has been removed.

Figure C.3. Energy of the transition states as function of the distance between C_2 and O_1 , $R^2 = 0.7178$. No point has been removed.

Figure C.4. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between C₂ and H, $R^2 = 0.0097$. No point has been removed.

Figure C.5. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between O₁ and H, $R^2 = 0.0307$. No point has been removed.

Figure C.6. Energy of the transition states as function of the angle between P, Cu₁ and O₁ and H, $R^2 = 0.6558$. No point has been removed.

Figure C.7. Energy of the transition states as function of the dihedral angle between Cu₁, N₁, N₂ and Cu₂, $R^2 = 0.4572$. No point has been removed.

Figure C.8. Energy of the transition states as function of the natural charge of Cu₁, R² = 0.6292. No point has been removed.

Figure C.9. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of Cu₂, R² = 0.0543. No point has been removed.

Figure C.10. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of the natural charge of Cu_1 and Cu_2 , $R^2 = 0.2375$. No point has been removed.

Figure C.11. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of C_2 , $R^2 = 0.0438$. No point has been removed.

Figure C.12. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of O₁, R² = 0.0173. No point has been removed.

Figure C.13. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of the natural charge of C₂ and O₁, R² = 0.0288. No point has been removed.

Figure C.14. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of H, $R^2 = 0.1564$. No point has been removed.

Figure C.15. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of the natural charge of C_2 and H, $R^2 = 0.1072$. No point has been removed.

Figure C.16. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of the natural charge of O₁ and H, R² = 0.0056. No point has been removed.

C - CuAAC reaction with 2^+ as catalyst

1) Step B: the formation of the triazolyl complex 15^+

The following figures are scatter plots showing the potential correlations between descriptors and the energy barriers. All the transition states related to the **TS₇** series are represented in blue dots.

Figure D.1. Energy of the TSs as function of the position of NTf_2^- . No point has been removed.

Figure D.2. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu_1 and Cu_2 , $R^2 = 0.0007$. No point has been removed.

Figure D.3. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between C_2 and N_3 , $R^2 = 0.0183$. No point has been removed.

Figure D.4. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between C₃ and N₅, R² = 0.0455. No point has been removed.

Figure D.5. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between C₂ and C₃, R² = 0.0506. No point has been removed.

Figure D.6. Energy of the TSs as function of the dihedral angle between Cu_1 , N_1 , N_2 and Cu_2 , $R^2 = 0.1509$. No point has been removed.

Figure D.7. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of Cu_1 , $R^2 = 0.0258$. No point has been removed.

Figure D.8. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of Cu_2 , $R^2 = 0.0216$. No point has been removed.

Figure D.9. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of the natural charge of Cu_1 and Cu_2 , $R^2 = 0.0097$. No point has been removed.

Figure D.10. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of C₂, R² = 0.0027. No point has been removed.

Figure D.11. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of C₃, R² = 0.0234. No point has been removed.

Figure D.12. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of N₃, R² = 0.3162. No point has been removed.

Figure D.13. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of N₅, R² = 0.0138. No point has been removed.

Figure D.14. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of the natural charge of C₂ and N₃, R² = 0.0054. The point [1.99;22.0] is not shown for clarity.

Figure D.15. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of the natural charge of C₃ and N₅, R² = 0.0006. The point [2.82;22.0] is not shown for clarity.

2) Step C: the regeneration of 2⁺ from 15⁺

The following figures are scatter plots showing the potential correlations between descriptors and the energy barriers. All the transition states related to the **TS₈**, **TS₉**, **TS₁₀** and **TS₁₁** series are represented in blue, green, orange and red dots, respectively.

Figure E.1. Energy of the TSs as function of the position of NTf_2^- . No point has been removed.

Figure E.2. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu_1 and Cu_2 , $R^2 = 0.0349$. The point [3.88;38.5] has been removed for clarity.

Figure E.3. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between C_2 and C_2' , $R^2 = 0.0869$. No point has been removed.

Figure E.4. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between C₂ and H, R² = 0.0141. The point [1.83;38.9] has been removed for clarity.

Figure E.5. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between C₂' and H, R² = 0.0521. No point has been removed.

Figure E.6. Energy of the TSs as function of the dihedral angle between Cu_1 , N_1 , N_2 and Cu_2 , $R^2 = 0.0175$. No point has been removed.

Figure E.7. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of Cu_1 , $R^2 = 0.1015$. No point has been removed.

Figure E.8. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of Cu_2 , $R^2 = 0.1986$. No point has been removed.

Figure E.9. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of the natural charge of Cu_1 and Cu_2 , $R^2 = 0.0008$. No point has been removed.

Figure E.10. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of C₂, R² = 0.3232. No point has been removed.

Figure E.11. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of C₂', R² = 0.1110. No point has been removed.

Figure E.12. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of H, $R^2 = 0.0835$. No point has been removed.

Figure E.13. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of the natural charge of C_2 and C_2' , $R^2 = 0.0048$. No point has been removed.

Figure E.14. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of the natural charge of C₂ and H, R² = 0.3081. No point has been removed.

Figure E.15. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of the natural charge of C₂' and H, R² = 0.0374. No point has been removed.

D - Ligand design: modifications on DPEOPN

1) Modification of the phosphine

The following figures are scatter plots showing the potential correlations between descriptors and the energy barriers. All the transition states related to the **TS_{B1R}** series are represented in blue dots while the ones related to the **TS_{B2R}** series are in green dots.

Figure F.1. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu_1 and Cu_2 , $R^2 = 0.0593$. No point has been removed.

Figure F.2. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of Cu_1 , $R^2 = 0.3250$. No point has been removed.

Figure F.3. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of Cu_2 , $R^2 = 0.0409$. No point has been removed.

Figure F.4. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of the natural charge of Cu₁ and Cu₂, R² = 0.3113. No point has been removed.

Figure F.5. Energy of the TSs as function of the dihedral angle between Cu₁, N₁, N₂ and Cu₂, R² = 0.0057. No point has been removed.

Figure F.6. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of C₁, R² = 0.0000. No point has been removed.

Figure F.7. Energy of the transition states as function of the natural charge of C₂, R² = 0.5676. No point has been removed.

Figure F.8. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of H, $R^2 = 0.0578$. No point has been removed.

Figure F.9. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu and C₁, $R^2 = 0.2650$. No point has been removed.

Figure F.10. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu and C₂, $R^2 = 0.2550$. No point has been removed.

Figure F.11. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between C₁ and H, $R^2 = 0.2063$. No point has been removed.

Figure F.12. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between C₂ and H, $R^2 = 0.3394$. No point has been removed.

Figure F.13. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu₁ and P, $R^2 = 0.0100$. No point has been removed.

Figure F.14. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of P, $R^2 = 0.2799$. No point has been removed.

Figure F.15. Energy of the TSs as function of the angle R-P-R, $R^2 = 0.0160$. No point has been removed.

2) Modifications of the pyridines

The following figures are scatter plots showing the potential correlations between descriptors and the energy barriers. All the transition states related to the TS_{D1Y} , TS_{D2Y} , TS_{E1Y} and TS_{E2Y} series are represented in blue, green, orange and red dots, respectively.

Figure G.1. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu_1 and Cu_2 , $R^2 = 0.1061$. No point has been removed.

Figure G.2. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of Cu_1 , $R^2 = 0.0007$. No point has been removed.

Figure G.3. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of Cu_2 , $R^2 = 0.0862$. No point has been removed.

Figure G.4. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of the natural charge of Cu₁ and Cu₂, R² = 0.0328. No point has been removed.

Figure G.5. Energy of the TSs as function of the dihedral angle between Cu₁, N₁, N₂ and Cu₂, R² = 0.0133. No point has been removed.

Figure G.6. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of C₁, R² = 0.0472. No point has been removed.

Figure G.7. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of C₂, R² = 0.0517. No point has been removed.

Figure G.8. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of H, $R^2 = 0.0000$. No point has been removed.

Figure G.9. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu and C_1 , $R^2 = 0.0690$. No point has been removed.

Figure G.10. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu and C₂, $R^2 = 0.3760$. No point has been removed.

Figure G.11. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between C₁ and H, $R^2 = 0.0929$. No point has been removed.

Figure G.12. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between C₂ and H, $R^2 = 0.0181$. No point has been removed.

Figure G.13. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu₂ and N₃, $R^2 = 0.1673$. No point has been removed.

Figure G.14. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu₂ and N₄, R² = 0.7882. No point has been removed.

Figure G.15. Energy of the TSs as function of the angle between N₃, Cu₂ and N₄, R² = 0.6644. No point has been removed.

Figure G.16. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of N_3 , $R^2 = 0.0402$. No point has been removed.

Figure G.17. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of N_4 , $R^2 = 0.1378$. No point has been removed.

3) Replacement of the pyridines by imines

The following figures are scatter plots showing the potential correlations between descriptors and the energy barriers. All the transition states related to the TS_{F1Y} , TS_{F2Y} , TS_{G1Y} and TS_{G2Y} series are represented in blue, green, orange and red dots, respectively.

Figure H.1. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu_1 and Cu_2 , $R^2 = 0.0005$. No point has been removed.

Figure H.2. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of Cu₁, R² = 0.1209. No point has been removed.

Figure H.3. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of Cu₂, R² = 0.0111. No point has been removed.

Figure H.4. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of the natural charge of Cu₁ and Cu₂, R² = 0.0650. No point has been removed.

Figure H.5. Energy of the TSs as function of the dihedral angle between Cu₁, N₁, N₂ and Cu₂, R² = 0.0358. No point has been removed.

Figure H.6. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of C₁, R² = 0.1844. No point has been removed.

Figure H.7. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of C₂, R² = 0.2980. No point has been removed.

Figure H.8. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of H, $R^2 = 0.0799$. No point has been removed.

Figure H.9. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu and C₁, $R^2 = 0.3890$. No point has been removed.

Figure H.10. Energy of the transition states as function of the distance between Cu and C₂, $R^2 = 0.6961$. No point has been removed.

Figure H.11. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between C₁ and H, $R^2 = 0.6134$. No point has been removed.

Figure H.12. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between C₂ and H, R² = 0.5470. No point has been removed.

Figure H.13. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu₂ and N₃, R² = 0.2852. No point has been removed.

Figure H.14. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu_2 and N_4 , $R^2 = 0.4832$. No point has been removed.

Figure H.15. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of N_3 , $R^2 = 0.0233$. No point has been removed.

Figure H.16. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of N₄, R² = 0.3570. No point has been removed.

Figure H.17. Energy of the TSs as function of the angle N₃-Cu₂-N₄, R² = 0.5218. No point has been removed.

4) Replacement of the pyridines by amines

The following figures are scatter plots showing the potential correlations between descriptors and the energy barriers. All the transition states related to the TS_{H1Y} , TS_{H2Y} , TS_{I1Y} and TS_{I2Y} series are represented in blue, green, orange and red dots, respectively.

Figure I.1. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu_1 and Cu_2 , $R^2 = 0.0335$. No point has been removed.

Figure I.2. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of Cu₁, R² = 0.0892. No point has been removed.

Figure I.3. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of Cu₂, R² = 0.0840. No point has been removed.

Figure I.4. Energy of the TSs as function of the difference of the natural charge of Cu₁ and Cu₂, R² = 0.1668. No point has been removed.

Figure I.5. Energy of the TSs as function of the dihedral angle between Cu₁, N₁, N₂, and Cu₂, R² = 0.0541. No point has been removed.

Figure I.6. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of C₁, R² = 0.3018. No point has been removed.

Figure I.7. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of C₂, R² = 0.0868. No point has been removed.

Figure I.8. Energy of the transition states as function of the natural charge of H, $R^2 = 0.6270$. No point has been removed.

Figure I.9. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu and C₁, $R^2 = 0.0046$. No point has been removed.

Figure I.10. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu and C₂, R² = 0.1136. No point has been removed.

Figure I.11. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between C₁ and H, R² = 0.1411. No point has been removed.

Figure I.12. Energy of the transition states as function of the distance between C₂ and H, R² = 0.5556. No point has been removed.

Figure I.13. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu₂ and N₃, R² = 0.0556. No point has been removed.

Figure I.14. Energy of the TSs as function of the distance between Cu_2 and N_4 , $R^2 = 0.0515$. No point has been removed.

Figure I.15. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of N_3 , $R^2 = 0.1953$. No point has been removed.

Figure I.16. Energy of the TSs as function of the natural charge of N₄, R² = 0.2209. No point has been removed.

Figure I.17. Energy of the TSs as function of the angle N₃-Cu₂-N₄, R² = 0.3527. No point has been removed.